

Smart Composites: Technological Characterisation of Optical Sensors(*)

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Abstract. Smart Composites are intended as composite materials with special sensors that can provide, in real time, informations upon variations of the principal mechanical parameters of the material.

Presently, optical sensors are the most employed within smart composites. These sensors, based on optical fibres inserted into the material, must be sensible to the variation of the stress, deformation, or other loads.

The technological compatibility of the sensors with the composite materials are some of the most important problems to be solved for the smart composites and the individuation of the appropriate optical parameter to correlate with mechanical load or deformation variations.

In this paper the Authors show the results of a study on the technological compatibility of the optical fibres with the temperature and pressure of polymerisation, and the results of experimental tests measuring variation of light attenuation on smart composite samples with a new special optical sensor.

The tests have been performed using pre-preg materials by hot pressing technologies, analysing the damage conditions affecting the fibres performance and evaluating the levels of the light attenuation.

Introduction.

Smart materials or smart structures can be defined [1,2,3] as materials or structures possessing adaptive capability to external stimuli such as load or environment.

Scientists have defined the concept of "smart materials and smart structures" in various ways for many fields of application.

The first studies were done during 1985, and now, however, the concept and the realisation of smart material or smart structures are not very clear.

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The birth and the development of such materials and structures are due to the development of opportune hardware and software systems for the elaboration of informations.

Smart structures can be employed in several fields of application, like in concrete bridge structures instrumented to monitor permanently the effect of the increasing traffic or ecological damages [4] or to monitor the effect of distributed stress as a function of position [5].

Another important application, in civil engineering, is to monitor the effects of seismic perturbations or the real behaviour of the structure and compare this with analytical and experimental models [6].

The smart composites could be employed in several fields as: marine applications, aerospace application and automotive applications.

One example of the possible application of smart composites in aeroplane are reported in fig. 1, as suggested by C. Boller et alii [7].

In this figure the dashed line indicates the network of sensors made by optical fiber.

Fig. 1 - Monitor of aeroplane [7]

This network is connected to a central data processing unit in the cockpit so that the operator can control the deterioration due to fatigue, corrosion, impacts, wear, or other environmental conditions or can modify the wing geometry for optimised aerodynamical behaviour including automated positioning of flaps and slats.

An exceptional result should be to use as sensors the fibers of the composite and thus to have an infinite number of sensors homogeneous distributed in the composite.

Presently, typical optical fiber diameters are 10 to 100 times larger than most reinforcing fiber diameters and thus it represents an important geometric discontinuity. The optical fiber acts as a physical intrusion and causes a structural degradation.

Jensen et al. [8] have shown that the presence of optical fibers, embedded in various orientations, reduces slightly the tensile properties of composite laminate while severely degrading the compression performance.

In the recent bibliography it is possible to find studies [9,10] regarding the possibility to correlate the mechanical properties of the composite materials with the optical parameters measured in the optical fibers embedded in the composite laminates.

The methods used, interferometric and polarimetric measurements, seem to be complicated: sophisticated equipment, advanced scientific and technical knowledge are necessarily requested.

In this paper the Authors show some results of a study on optical fiber compatibility with the temperature and pressure values used during the fabrication of composite materials.

The initial performance of a sensor, based on optical fibers, is also shown. In our tests the optical parameter correlated with the imposed deflection is the variation of the luminous attenuation.

Technological compatibility

Technological compatibility of optical fibers with the most important parameters, as temperature and pressure, of the fabrication methods of composite materials have been analyzed. The possibility to use the optical fiber itself as sensor has in fact been considered in this phase.

It is opportune to recall that the optical fiber is constituted by an internal "core" and an external "cladding": the brittle fiber is thus coated with opportune coating materials. As it is used to transmit luminous signal within the core of the fiber, the function of the cladding is to guide and to confine the signal into the core.

Multi mode 100/140 μm and 50/125 μm optical fibers coated with acrylate for a 250 μm nominal diameter, produced by Fibre Ottiche Sud spa, have been used.

The fibers have been subjected to preliminar tests under 15 minutes thermal cycling composed by heating and cooling, for a total time of 2 hours, between R.T. and a temperature of 150 °C. The conditions of the fibers was ascertained by a simple test go-not-go with a low intensity light. This test has demonstrated that the core and the cladding are not damaged by the thermal variation, whereas the acrylate coating loses its properties at approximately 85 °C.

Samples of composite materials with embedded optical fibers have been prepared with manual laying-up prepreg carbon fabric 0/90° and the curing has been carried-out by hot-plane press with a temperature of 120 °C for 2 hours and a pressure between 2 and 10 daN/cm².

Two series of samples have been prepared for each type of optical fiber using coated fibers and not coated fibers obtained removing the acrylate coating by a chemical method.

Two types of composite laminate have been tested:

- a) (0/90)₂/optical fiber/(0/90)₁₄
- b) (0/90)/0/0/optical fiber/0/0/(0/90)₂₀.

The thickness of the specimens were respectively of 3 mm and 3.5 mm

In the first case the optical fibers have positioned between fabric layers while in the second case the optical fibers have positioned on unidirectional fibers and oriented parallel to the graphite fibers.

During the fabrication of the composite laminates have carried-out test go-not-go. All the optical fibers, coated or not coated with acrylate, positioned between fabric layers do not transmit the luminous signal. The fabric layers causes a particular regular micro-bending on the optical fibers. This micro-bending impedes the transmission of the luminous signal; in fact the regular micro deformations of the fibers cause the presence of particular multiple reflections so that the fiber becomes blind.

It is important to note that the fibers do not present mechanical fractures.

All specimens with unidirectional layers do transmit the light signal. A three-point flexural test was performed on these composite samples that have surpassed the go-not-go test. The scheme of the equipment used for the flexural test is shown in figure 2. One end of the optical fiber is connected with a source light (laser) while the other end is connected with a power meter to measure a luminous attenuation.

Fig. 2 - Scheme of three-point flexural equipment test.

The luminous attenuation and the sample deflection for some loading cycles were measured. A typical diagram attenuation versus deflection for coated optical fiber with acrylate is reported in figure 3. The optical fiber is deformed during the flexion of the samples; this deformation causes a variation of the light propagation mode. Consequently, the attenuation increases.

After 8-10 loading cycles it is noted that the attenuation change independently by the deflection as showed in figure 3. This behaviour is due to the degradation of the acrylate coating that causes a micro sliding of the

optical fiber with respect to the composite. The curves reported in fig. 3 is referred to a pressure of 2 daN/cm².

Increasing the value of the pressure, used during the fabrication of the laminates, until 10 daN/cm² it has observed the reduction of the light attenuation with the deflection of the samples and a high dependence of the attenuation with the deformation speed.

Fig. 3 - Attenuation versus deflection for coated optical fibers .

The behaviour of the samples with non coated fibers has been reported in fig. 4.

Fig. 4 - Attenuation versus deflection for not coated optical fibers

In this case it is not possible to find any relation between the attenuation and the deflection. Certainly, the uncoated fiber is subjected directly to a micro bendings and micro fractures that alter, in random way, the optical response of the fiber.

To avoid the problems connected with the acrylate degradation it can use a coating more resistant as polyimide coating can be used. This type of coating moreover allows to maintain perfect the circular shape of the core and of the cladding [11].

In all the cases it is possible to note that the values of the attenuation are very low and uncertainties in the attenuation measures do exist. Moreover, the connections between the optical fiber embedded in the laminate and the laser source and the power meter causes a luminous signal attenuation of the same magnitude order of that found in the fiber.

Optical sensors

The variation of the light attenuation in the optical fibers is too low and for this reason the optical fibers generally seem not utilizable itself as sensor. However, starting from the above experience, two sensors based on micro bending phenomena of optical fibers have been proposed.

The first type is an internal sensor embedded into the composite laminate. This sensor, figure 5, is constituted by a hard wire helicoidally wound around on the optical fiber. It is necessary to have a perfect contact between the hard wire and the optical fiber avoiding that the resin, during the polymerisation of the laminate, can prevent this contact.

The hard wire has been blocked on the optical fiber using a spray paint resistant to high temperature. Multi mode 100/140 μm optical fibers with acrylate coating were used. Polymerisation temperature was of 85 °C to avoid melting of the acrylate coating.

Fig. 5 - Internal sensor

The second type is an external sensor. The scheme of the sensor is shown in figure 6. This sensor is constituted by two thin layers that act on the optical fiber. A hard wire is wound around the optical fiber as for the internal sensor.

The external sensor is based on the sample surface. Flexural tests with the equipment shown in the figure 2 have been carried out. During the tests the sensors have been subjected to tensile stresses.

The typical behaviours of the internal and external sensors are reported in figure 7.

Fig. 6 - Scheme of external sensor

Fig. 7 - Attenuation versus deflection for internal and external sensors

It is possible to observe that for the internal sensor the variation of the attenuation is two orders of magnitude larger than that measured in the optical fiber used itself as sensor.

The difference between the internal and external sensor is due to the difficulty to transfer the deformation from the sample to the optical fiber of the sensor.

Conclusions

The optical fibers are compatible with the levels of temperature and pressure used during the fabrication of composite laminate. To avoid the

melting of the coatings it is necessary to use coatings resistant to high temperature as polyimide coatings. Acrylate coating is utilizable for curing temperature not higher than 85° C.

The tests have demonstrated that it is not possible to use optical fibers itself as deformation sensors, because the attenuation of the luminous signal is too small and the results are not repeatable.

Internal and external sensors have been proposed and the first results show that it is possible to have high variation of the light attenuation.

These sensors are based on the micro bending phenomena of the optical fibers. Micro deformations cause the variations of the light reflections in the optical fibers and thus the attenuation of the luminous signal increase.

It is observed that special micro bending, as those created by the fabric layers, causes the blinding of the optical fibers. It is necessary further study of the conditions that cause the blinding of the optical fiber when used as optical sensors.

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